

Original Research Article

Factors Influencing in the Educational Environment among Nursing Students

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Abstract

Educational environment impact on students learning with various ways like hands on learning related to teacher supervision, learning attitudes of students, atmosphere of the school and weakness in learning impact on student's education positively and negatively. The aim of the study is to determine the factors influencing in educational environment among nursing students. Cross sectional study was done in Lahore School of Nursing, the University of Lahore and the study duration was 4 months from September 2019 to December 2019. The 135 students participated in this study and 5 Likert scales from 1-5 were used to evaluate the educational environment among nursing students. Tool was adopted from Messas et al. (2016) which were used to collect data in Lahore School of nursing. The data collected through questionnaire was calculated through statistical package for social science version 21 for descriptive statistics The study findings showed that factor 1 support for hands on learning with mean score of 3.62, factor 2 attitude during learning with mean score of 3.10, factor 3 learning atmosphere with mean score 3.28 and final factor 4 learning weakness with mean score of 3.22. Nursing students gave highest score to factor 1 support for hands on leaning and factor 2 attitudes during learning was low so this factor need more strengthening for undergraduate nursing students.

Keywords: Educational Environment, Attitude during Learning, Learning Atmosphere and weakness in learning

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INTRODUCTION

Educational environment in nursing involves both hands-on and theoretical education. In addition, for nursing students educational environment should encourage critical thinking and lifetime knowledge. Educational environment impact on students learning with various ways. Student perception about their educational environment, like hands on learning related to teacher supervision, learning attitudes of students, atmosphere of the school and weakness in learning impact on student's education positively and negatively. These factors help out students to achieve their goals efficiently. Educational environment and students expectations support the student's action and encourage for social interaction, inside and outside the school that enhance interpersonal relationship with teachers and meet the learning goals

(Mthimunye and Daniels, 2019).

Assistance provided by clinical supervision helps students connect theoretical classroom knowledge to the care of patients in the clinical environment (Donough and van der Heever, 2018). Clinical supervision is beneficial for students. First of all, by directly monitored students at clinical environment, The supportive relationship is built between the clinicians Supervisor and student (Bifarin and Stonehouse, 2017). Clinical supervision promotes positive attitude toward student's wellbeing, professional development and contributes to the need for lifelong learning and confidence (Fuvich, 2017).

Clinical supervision is a procedure of assistant and knowledge which allows the students to grow their knowledge and skill for their own rehearsal, and improve

patient care and well-being in complicated clinical circumstances. Hands on learning become effective with teacher supervision. Therefore, to fill the gap among academic learning and its implementation in clinical learning many educational helpful models like clinical supervision was established (Dehghani et al., 2016).

Educational environment is how the student reflects about climate of an institution. It includes their awareness regarding educational environment like infrastructure of the organization, educational opportunities, teacher's behavior and supervision, student's attitude about learning, educational atmosphere, weakness in learning and many other factors. Educational environment play a very important role on student education. Good educational environment is the reflective of quality course (Sarwar and Tarique, 2016).

The classroom is a setting where students understand key concepts related to clinical practice. Classroom learning is influenced by teacher characteristics, written assignments, classroom environment, curriculum, and motivations. It is important for nursing students to enhance their knowledge and skills in classroom and clinical learning, which helps students care for patients in the clinical setting (Setati and Nkosi, 2017).

Problem Statement

Many studies had been conducted in India, UK, Brazil, and Iran on factors influencing clinical and academic environment that include both clinical and academic environment related factors such as support for hands on learning, learning attitude, learning weakness and learning atmosphere. Some studies have been conducted on educational environment of nursing students in Pakistan. In order to achieve successful and effective educational and academic environment there is need for study to investigate factor influencing educational environment among nursing students.

Significance of the study

This study will provide sufficient information about the factors affecting the educational environment in nursing students. This researcher can benefit by enabling students to understand the factors that may influencing the educational environment for teachers, this investigation may enable them to understand the student-driven issues that may influencing educational environment. Nurse students' excellent performance during the training period reveals academic quality. This study will be a source of information to improve awareness of factors affecting the nursing profession, as well as their practice at the clinical site. This study will encourage and enhance the learning attitude of nursing students in the classroom and clinical placement that is

overall educational environment .This study will help the institute (Lahore School of Nursing) to appropriate managing the factors providing quality nurse for future.

Literature search

A Study identified the ethics of education through beliefs and practices from the perspective of psychologists. The results showed that the ethics of education included a set of behaviors and beliefs, such as course content, evaluation of students, academic environment, disrespect, research and financial (Tabachnick et al., 2016).

The most common influences affecting the nursing students learning. These factors associated to the educator's factors. The student factor, the household, school, the nursing students' educational performance significantly. And affects the gender of the participant is negatively related to the education of the participants because the value of sealing value (Fajar et al., 2019).

The results of this study revealed that the most important factors affecting educational performance were personal attitudes 78%, teachers' personality 50%, and understanding of subject 89%. Resource availability atmosphere of the school affects 78% of learners' academic performance (Sharma et al., 2017).

The study highlights the strengths and weaknesses of an educational institution, comparing its performance and effectiveness. There are many issues that need to be changed and the social students' perception of the 'students' school is not worse. There were no individual fields of excellence (Item Score> 3.5) in nursing student (Hettiarachchi and Chandana, 2012).

The study was done in India (2011) Most nursing students in the classroom were not satisfied with the teachers' learning style. However, 25% of the nursing students were satisfied. However, teachers' effective learning style increases the motivation for classroom learning in nursing students (Wijnia et al., 2011).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Showing Maslow hierarchy of needs

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A quantitative cross sectional study was conducted.

Study Site

The study was conducted in Lahore school of Nursing, The University of Lahore.

Duration

Study duration was 4month from September 2019 January 2020.

Population

The population of this study was the nursing students. The students of 4 year Bachelor of Science in nursing BSN degree program and BSN (Post RN) from Lahore School of Nursing were the population of research study.

Sampling

A convenient sampling method was used for this study. It is type of non-probability sampling in which sample is extracted from part of population that is easily available and closes to hand.

Research Instrument

Questionnaire adopted from (Messas et al., 2016) was used to collect data from nursing students of Lahore School of Nursing Questionnaires.

Data Gathering Procedure

Questionnaires consist of 5 section, Section A was Demographic Data Section B was Hands on learning related to supervision Section C was Attitude towards learning Section D was composed on learning atmosphere and Section E was learning weakness. The participants answered the items using 5-point Likert scale with 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = neutral 4=agree 5=strongly agree. The data collected through questionnaire was calculated through statistical package for social science version 21 for descriptive statistics using mean, frequency, percentage and standard deviation.

Ethical Consideration

The rules and regulations set by the ethical committee of university of Lahore will be followed while conducting the research and the rights of the research participants will be respected. Permission for data collection was taken from all the participants on attached consent form. All the data and information taken from students was kept in confidential. Throughout the study participants were remain anonymous. It is informed that no disadvantages and risk of the study were considered. Participants were informed that any time they will free hand to with draw from process of study.

RESULTS

This chapter consists of two sections. Section 1 represent Demographic Data the study Participants, Section 2 consists of graphical representation of factor influencing the educational environment, (1) Hands on learning related to supervision (2) Attitudes towards learning (3) learning atmosphere and (4)learning weakness. The data collected through questionnaire were calculated through statistical package for social science version 21 for descriptive statistics using mean, frequency, percentage and standard deviation.

Section 1

This section represents the distribution of participant by demographic characteristics. The data is summarized in terms of frequency and percentage.

Table 1 elaborates the percentage and frequencies of demographic characteristics of the participants that majority of student involved in this study were female n = 122 (90.4%), and male were n = 13 (9.6%). The frequency of female is higher than male in this study. The majority of participants involved in this study were n = 127 (94.1%) belong to the age group 18 to 26 years and n=8 (5.9%) belong to the age group 27 to 35 years. participants involved in this study were n = 48 (35.6%) were 1st year student, n = 47 (34.8%) were 2nd year, n = 29 (21.5%) were 3rd year and n = 11 (8.1%) were 4th year. n = 117 (86.7%) participants were belong to BSN 4 years program and n = 18 (13.3%) belong to BSN post RN 2years.

Section 2

This section represents data about factors influencing educational environment of nursing student. Factors (1) Hands on learning related to supervision (2) Attitudes towards learning (3) learning atmosphere and (4) learning weakness. Statistical analysis was carried out using

Table 1. Description of Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Respondents	
	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	13	9.6%
Female	122	90.4%
Age (years)		
18 to 26years	127	94.1%
27 to 35	8	5.9%
year_of_study		
1st year	48	35.6%
2nd year	47	34.8%
3rd year	29	21.5%
4th year	11	8.1%
Course		
BSN post RN 2years	18	13.3%
BSN 4 years	117	86.7%

Table 2. Factor 1: support for hands on learning

Statement	D f (%)	NDNA f (%)	A f (%)
Teachers were present whenever I needed them.	9 (6.7)	40 (29.6)	86 (63.7)
I feel confident about the supervision of the teachers.	9 (6.7)	40 (29.6)	86 (63.7)
I have been encouraged to participate in work.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
Field provided conditions for carrying out the activities planned.	29 (21.5)	20 (14.8)	86 (63.7)
I feel confident about the supervision of the nurses.	24 (17.8)	40 (29.6)	71 (52.6)

Table 3. Factor 2: Attitude during learning

Statement	D f (%)	NDNA f (%)	A f (%)
I have witnessed the occurrence of situations that disregard ethical aspects of professional practice.	25 (18.6)	40 (29.6)	76 (56.3)
I notice unethical actions by some teachers.	39 (28.9)	20 (14.8)	76 (56.3)
I have not always been received very well by the nursing staff in the fields of practice.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
Teachers do not listen to the students.	60 (44.5)	60 (44.4)	15 (11.1)
Teachers get irritated with the behavior of students.	60 (44.5)	40 (29.6)	35 (25.9)
The opinion of the students is considered in order to improve the teaching process.	49 (36.3)	20 (14.8)	66 (48.9)
Student performance evaluation does not occur continuously.	95 (70.4)	20 (14.8)	20 (14.8)
Mentoring offers the support that students need.	25 (18.6)	20 (14.8)	90 (66.6)

Table 4. Factor 3: Learning Atmosphere

Statement	D f (%)	NDNA f (%)	A f (%)
The learning environment is stimulating.	44 (32.6)	20 (14.8)	71 (52.6)
I concentrate on other things during the lectures	60 (44.5)	20 (14.8)	55 (40.7)
This course is meeting my expectations.	49 (36.3)	40 (29.6)	46 (34.1)
The people of this School are caring.	64 (47.4)	20 (14.8)	51 (37.8)
This school is welcoming.	64 (47.4)	20 (14.8)	51 (37.8)
Teachers help me find learning opportunities.	84 (62.2)	20 (14.8)	31 (23.0)
The course has been important in my training.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
Previous semesters has facilitated my development in the current semester.	9 (6.7)	20 (14.8)	106 (78.5)
Able to discuss the ethical and legal aspects related to the professional practice.	44 (32.6)	55 (40.7)	36 (26.7)
The course has provided gradual development of my professional identity.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
I have good interactions with the teachers.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
I feel comfortable giving my views during the theoretical and practical classes.	44 (32.6)	20 (14.8)	71 (52.6)
The classes are held in a pleasant atmosphere.	9 (6.7)	40 (29.6)	86 (63.7)
Teachers and students respect one another.	29 (21.5)	36 (26.7)	70 (51.8)
The information given by the School's employees is confusing.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
I have good contact with classmates from other semesters.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)

descriptive statistics such as table, frequency and percentage.

Table 2 showed statistics regarding support for hands on learning result indicated that respondents highly response "Agree" to item (1, 2, and 3). Item 4 high response to "Agreed" the fields have provided conditions for carrying out the activities planned. And 52.6% respondents agreed supervision of nurses provide confident.

Table 3 showed the results factor 2 that is attitude during learning respondents high response in form of "agree" in reaction to (1, 2, 3, 6, 8) item because respondents high response to "Disagree" in reaction to (4, 5 and 7).

Table 3 revealed the results regarding learning atmosphere that is necessary for educational

environment 52.6% of the respondents agreed that learning environment is stimulating. Respondents highly disagreed to item (2, 4, 5, 6). Neutral respondents were 29.6%, 40.7% to item (3, 9). Participants disagreed to item (7, 8, 10, and 11) also respondents highly disagreed to item (13, 14 and 15).

Table 5 showed the response of participants about weakness in learning they high response in form of "agrees" to item (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5). 58.5% respondents disagreed that I am not able to make friends in this School. The objectives proposed for my professional training are clear 6, 7% disagreed to this statement. The respondents' high response to agree in reaction to item (8, 10) and 74% disagreed to statement I still don't know what the nurse's role is.

Table 5. Factor 4: weakness in learning

Statement	D f (%)	NDNA f (%)	A f (%)
Courses have been known by memorization.	24 (17.8)	40 (29.6)	71 (52.6)
I don't feel I have leisure time due to fatigue Courses.	24 (17.8)	20 (14.8)	91 (67.4)
Carry out activities for which I do not feel prepared.	44 (32.6)	20 (14.8)	71 (52.6)
I have more access to the School's labs.	24 (17.8)	40 (29.6)	71 (52.6)
Classes are taught exclusively with slide presentation.	9 (6.7)	20 (14.8)	106 (78.5)
I am not able to make friends in this School.	79 (58.5)	40 (29.6)	16 (11.9)
Objectives for my professional training are clear	9 (6.7)	40 (29.6)	86 (63.7)
I don't understand why they are teaching certain subjects.	29 (21.5)	20 (14.8)	86 (63.7)
I still don't know what the nurse's role is.	100 (74)	20 (14.8)	15 (11.1)
decision-making are not encouraged by the teachers.	9 (6.7)	40 (29.6)	86 (63.7)

Table 6. Distribution of scores by factor

Factors	N	M	SD	Standard Error
F1	135	3.62	1.088	0.05
F2	135	3.10	1.160	0.09975
F3	135	3.281	1.138	0.0978
F4	135	3.22	1.0266	0.0884

ANOVA test

The ANOVA results showed variations in all scores levels when the current semester was comparison variable. Factor 1 [F (3.166) = 5.166, $p \leq 0.01$] Factor 3 [F (3.166) = 4.348, $p \leq 0.01$], Factor 2 [F (3.166) = 22.014, $p \leq 0.01$]; and Factor 4 [F (3.166) = 4.243, $p \leq 0.01$]. There were no other significant difference between year of the study and factors.

DISCUSSION

The objective of the study was to determine the factors influencing in the educational environment among nursing students. The data was collected from 135 BSN 4 years and BSN (post RN) nursing students of Lahore school of nursing. In this study gender score for female was high with 90.4% and male was 9.6% that was low as compare to female. The study participants were 1st year students who were in 2nd semester, 2nd year students who were in 4th semester, 3rd year students were in 6th semester and 4th year students were in final semester.

The study showed that highest score went to factor 1 that is support for hands on learning, and attitude during learning was lowest score that is factor 2. Mean score for factor 1 was ± 3.62 while mean score for factor 2 was ± 3.10 .

The results of the study show that with regard to factors 1 and 3, Support for hands on learning and learning atmosphere Scores were higher than factors 2 and 4, attitude during learning and learning weakness. All these factors are interdependent therefore, will be discussed in coordinated manners.

In Factor 2, attitude during learning was significantly lower on average in the second semester group as compared to other groups. The sixth semester group achieved high scores in this factor, with significant differences from the other groups. Learning atmosphere that is Factor 3 the average of the sixth semester group was significantly lower than the other groups. The eighth semester achieved high scores in this factor, with significant differences from the other groups.

As a final point, Factor 4 that is learning weakness the average for the eighth semester was significantly lower than the other semesters, while the sixth semester scored the highest scores in this factor, with significant

differences from the other groups. Mean score for factor 3 was 3.28 while mean score for factor 4 was ± 3.22 that was lower than mean score of factor 3.

In this study, support for hands on learning among nursing students was confirmed, particularly in case of supervision, teachers were there and encouraged students to take part in clinical setting. These findings expose the consideration of school to provide support to the students in practical learning as well as academic learning. Another study showed the results of confidence and practical teaching of nursing students increase with the teacher supervision and behavior (MUNAWAR et al., 2017). Student and teacher relationship is important along with listening to students by the teachers.

In this study, learning atmosphere was estimated, such as Learning atmosphere is considered satisfying, friendly and good relationship with teachers. Good relationship with teachers leads to reflection and discussion with teachers. Though, students also give emphasis to improve the direction provided by practical and organization experts.

In some studies, good relationships between students and teachers have been highlighted which showed a direct link between good relationships and professional development of students (Messas et al., 2016). An important feature of the learning atmosphere is providing students with the strategies that help them covenant with moral concerns.

The study reveals that strategies used in teaching learning process needs to take into account all the changes in the teacher's work process such as time, motivation, dedication, communication and more importantly to adopt these strategies. Adoption of proactive methodology is a weakness in the educational environment during school evaluation. Because teaching strategies are based on memorization and knowledge delivery, which may explain the lack of understanding of the material offered for the practical training of students and clarity in role of the nurse.

In educational environment to support teaching learning strategies it is essential to provide favorable environment to teacher students to establish a good interaction and to develop new strategies. Some facets, as well as the values of meaningful learning and methodologies in learning, guide students with opportunities for education, thus facilitating the role of facilitators in this process. Most favorable factor from student's viewpoint was support for hands on learning. Attitude during learning received lower scores as compare to other factors so there is need to support these scores in undergraduate nursing students. Although there is an argument about respect for students and the moral concerns that arise.

CONCLUSION

In summary, to determine the factors influencing in the educational environment among nursing students. In four factors the most favorable factor from student's perspective was support for hands on learning in educational environment. This factor involves student's opinion to promote education and develop student's confidence to make good interaction with teachers. In regarding to teaching strategies supporting students help to make good strategies used in educational environment as slides presentations also help in memorization. Students were aware with role of nurse professional issues it indicated that course objectives were meeting the needs of student. And factor 2 attitudes during learning gain lower score it suggested that respect should be given to students. The responsibility of institute and teachers is to meet the needs of students by providing favorable educational environment to nursing students.

Strength of the Study

The study has following strength

- This is a first study conducted in Lahore school of nursing on both clinical and academic environment among nursing students.
- The questionnaire used in this study was already been tested for validity and reliability.
- Correct data was collected with full cooperation of student.

Limitations

The study has following limitations that essential to be acknowledged in explanation of results.

- The data collected for this study is collected only on setting that is not enough to generalizability.
- Convenient sampling is used.
- The study is limited to determine the factors influencing in the educational environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to noted study results, following strategies should be recommended to provide educational environment according to student need and pay attention to lower factor by the institute and teachers.

- Provide supportive practice to the nursing students on clinical and academic level
- On the bases of student work and performance students should be involved in teaching learning process.
- Provide opportunity for students to establish better relationship between teacher and students

- Pay proper attention to student's attitude during learning
- Enhance positive work environment by collaboration, establish trust and respect

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